

Technical – Tactical Analysis of XXXII Summer Olympic Games and 2022 World Championship Freestyle Wrestling Competitions

XXXII. Yaz Olimpiyat Oyunları ve 2022 Dünya Şampiyonası Serbest Güreş Müsabakalarının Teknik – Taktik Analizi

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Abstract

The aim of the present study was to compare notational technical-tactical analysis of the XXXII Summer Olympic Games (OG) and 2022 World Championship (WC) freestyle wrestling competitions. A total of 293 (103 OG and 190 WC) videos of bouts were watched and analyzed by the Dartfish Connect Plus 8.0 match analysis program. Bout analyses were performed according to 1) bout analysis preparation, 2) searching and tagging, 3) database creation, and 4) data usage procedures. Wrestling techniques were grouped into takedowns and throws in standing position and flips and throws in parterre position. Points were determined according to time and periods, standing and parterre position, winning types, attacks, and counter-attacks. There is a significant difference between attacks and counter-attacks in WC and OG ($p < 0.05$; $\chi^2 = 31.689$). The types of victories in WC and OG are 63.7% and 73.8% by point, respectively. In the first and second periods, technical points are determined according to wrestling actions (WAmean) 1.74 and 1.76 ($t = 0.488$, Cohen's $d = .031$), 1.66 and 1.69 ($t = 0.567$, Cohen's $d = .048$) in WC and OG, respectively. Most wrestling techniques are performed in the standing position (WC 58.8% and OG 68.2%). Leg Attack is the most used technique in the standing position (WC 17.9% and OG 21.8%). In conclusion, techniques that earn two points, attack movements, performed at the standing position, such as leg attack, take down, and push to out, are important in elite wrestling matches.

Keywords wrestling, performance, match analyses, elite athlete.

Öz

Bu çalışmanın amacı, XXXII. Yaz Olimpiyat Oyunları (OG) ile 2022 Dünya Şampiyonası (WC) serbest güreş müsabakalarının notasyonel teknik-taktik analizlerini karşılaştırmaktır. Toplam 293 (103 OG ve 190 WC) güreş müsabakasına ait video görüntüsü Dartfish Connect Plus 8.0 maç analiz programı kullanılarak izlenmiş ve analiz edilmiştir. Müsabaka analizleri; 1) analiz ön hazırlığı, 2) arama ve etiketleme, 3) veri tabanı oluşturma ve 4) veri kullanımı aşamalarına göre gerçekleştirilmiştir. Güreş teknikleri, ayakta yapılan teknikler (dalma, itme, fırlatma) ile parter pozisyonundaki teknikler (çevirmeler ve fırlatmalar) şeklinde gruplandırılmıştır. Ayrıca zaman ve periyotlara göre puan dağılımları, ayakta ve parter pozisyonlarındaki puanlar, galibiyet türleri, atak ve kontra-ataklar analiz edilmiştir. OG ve WC müsabakaları arasında atak ve kontrataklar bakımından anlamlı fark bulunmuştur ($p < 0.05$; $\chi^2 = 31.689$). Galibiyet türü olarak WC'de %63.7, OG'de ise %73.8 oranında puanla kazanım gözlemlenmiştir. Teknik puan ortalamaları açısından, birinci ve ikinci periyotlarda güreş aksiyonlarına (WAmean) göre sırasıyla WC'de 1.74 ve 1.66; OG'de 1.76 ve 1.69 değerleri tespit edilmiştir ($t = 0.488$, Cohen's $d = .031$; $t = 0.567$, Cohen's $d = .048$). Tekniklerin büyük çoğunluğu ayak pozisyonunda uygulanmıştır (WC %58.8, OG %68.2). Ayak pozisyonunda en sık uygulanan teknik ise ayağa dalmalar olarak görülmüştür (WC %17.9, OG %21.8). Sonuç olarak, iki puan kazandıran teknikler, ayak pozisyonunda uygulanan atak hareketleri (ayağa dalmalar, ayaktan indirmeler ve dışarı itme gibi) elit düzey güreş müsabakalarında belirleyici olmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler güreş, performans, maç analizi, elit sporcu

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Introduction

Wrestling is one of the oldest known sports, with origins tracing back to the Sumerians approximately 5,000 years ago. Today, it is practiced in various forms across many regions of the world. As one of the foundational sports of the Ancient Olympic Games, wrestling was incorporated into the modern Olympic program beginning in 1896, with freestyle wrestling becoming a recognized discipline. Since 2002, the governance of wrestling has been overseen by United World Wrestling (UWW) (García-Pallarés et al., 2011; United World Wrestling [UWW], 2023).

The development of appropriate and optimized training methodologies is fundamental to achieving success in wrestling (Chaabene et al., 2017; Yoon, 2002). A wrestler's performance in competition is largely influenced by their level of technical and tactical proficiency (Tropin, 2013). Therefore, analyzing matches at the elite level is essential for the evolution of both training practices and technical–tactical innovations. The coaching process is inherently aimed at enhancing athletic performance by delivering effective feedback to athletes and teams (James, 2009). However, in combat sports such as wrestling, where the dynamics of the match involve direct physical engagement, it is exceedingly challenging (even for experienced coaches) to observe, recall, and interpret all critical moments of a match or training session accurately. This limitation applies equally to athletes, whose perception of performance events may be influenced by cognitive biases or limited visual information (Farwell, 2013; Ciprano, 1993; Podlivaev, 2010; Shakhmuradov, 2011).

According to Tünnemann (1996), optimizing the effectiveness of training is a central objective in improving performance in combat sports. A critical component of this process involves setting clear performance targets, predicting outcomes, and conducting systematic performance analysis. Performance Analysis (PA) refers to the application of structured methods to measure and evaluate athletic performance. Typically conducted through video-based systems (both manual and computerized) PA encompasses the technical–tactical and biomechanical examination of athlete behavior during and after training or competition (James, 2009). The goal of PA is to establish a reliable and valid record of performance through objective observation, thereby facilitating meaningful feedback. Well-designed performance indicators offer practical insights by highlighting strengths and weaknesses in technique or strategic execution, supporting comparative assessments between athletes or teams (Hughes & Franks, 2007; McGarry et al., 2013).

Numerous studies have investigated technical–tactical aspects of wrestling across different tournaments and championships (Arabacı et al., 2018; Atan & İmamoğlu, 2005; Kajmovic et al., 2014; López-González, 2013; López-González, 2014; Miarka, 2016; Shakhmuradov, 2011; Tünnemann, 2016). However, due to the frequent revisions in wrestling rules by the UWW, these analyses must be periodically updated to remain relevant. In addition, the constant evolution of techniques and training methodologies necessitates ongoing research in this area. To the best of our knowledge, following the most recent rule modifications by UWW, there remains a lack of comparative research analyzing technical–tactical parameters between the XXXII Summer Olympic Games and the 2022 World Wrestling Championships.

Therefore, the primary aim of the present study was to conduct a comparative notational analysis of technical–tactical parameters observed in freestyle wrestling matches from the XXXII Summer Olympic Games and the 2022 World Championships.

Materials And Methods

Sample

Freestyle wrestling competitions from the XXXII Olympic Games (OG), held in Tokyo in 2021, and the 2022 World Wrestling Championships (WC), held in Belgrade, were analyzed using the Dartfish Connect Plus 8.0 match analysis software. The notational technical–tactical analysis of the bouts was conducted by the first and second authors, both of whom have over ten years of experience as wrestlers and certified wrestling coaches.

The analysis included matches from weight categories common to both tournaments: 57 kg, 65 kg, 74 kg, 86 kg, 97 kg, and 125 kg. Weight categories contested only at the WC—61 kg, 70 kg, 79 kg, and 92 kg—were excluded from the analysis, as they are not part of the Olympic competition program. This study was supported by the Scientific Research Projects Unit of Bursa Uludağ University (Project Number: SGA-2021-356, Date: 14.04.2021). The data used in this study were obtained from the 2021 and 2022 Senior Freestyle World Championship competition results and statistics, which are publicly available and published on the official website of United World Wrestling. Therefore, ethics committee approval is not required.

Procedures

The match analyses were conducted according to the following four-step procedure:

Preparation: Defining the type and structure of the analysis. A model template for technical–tactical performance analysis was created.

Searching and Tagging: Identifying the relevant sequences, actions, or behaviors to be analyzed; labeling these behaviors; and delimiting each instance.

Database Creation: Categorizing each parameter and generating summary tables.

Data Utilization: Performing statistical analyses, presenting the results, and preparing the final report (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Study workflow.

Technical–Tactical Combinations

The techniques were categorized into two nominal groups: attack and counter-attack. An Attack Coefficient (A/C Coefficient) was calculated by dividing the number of attacks by the number of counter-attacks. Techniques were grouped into; Takedowns and throws (standing position), Flips and throws (parterre position).

Quantitative Indicators of Technical–Tactical Performance

Diversity: Number of different techniques used per match (techniques/match)

Effectiveness: Frequency of applied technical–tactical combinations per match (TTC/match)

Efficiency: Total points scored per minute of wrestling (points/minute)

Technical–Tactical Indicators

Standing/Parterre Coefficient: Ratio of techniques executed from the standing to those executed from the parterre position

Type of Struggle: Actions were categorized into pushing, pulling, and active movement

Performance Parameters Analyzed

The following parameters were examined (see Figure 2 for an example of the tagging screen in Dartfish): Points scored by time interval and period, Points earned in standing vs. parterre positions, Types of techniques, Methods of victory, Incidences of passivity and cautions.

Figure 2. Wrestling bout analysis and tagging screen e.g.

Statistical Analyses

Quantitative and qualitative data from the Dartfish Connect Plus 8.0 software were transferred to SPSS for Windows (version 27.0; IBM Corp., Armonk, NY) for statistical analysis. The following tests were employed depending on the data structure: Independent Samples t-test, Chi-square test, One-way ANOVA, Univariate Analysis of Variance. Where appropriate, Bonferroni post hoc tests were conducted following one-way ANOVA. Effect sizes for the t-tests were interpreted using Cohen's d: small (0.20), medium (0.50), and large (0.80). Effect sizes for ANOVA and Univariate Analysis of Variance were assessed using Partial Eta Squared (η^2_p): small (0.10), medium (0.25), and large (0.80). The p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Frequencies of attack and counter-attack techniques performed by wrestlers were determined to be 649 (78%) and 183 (22%) in WC, 452 (87.9%) and 62 (12.1%) in OG, respectively. There is a significant difference between attack and counter-attacks frequencies in WC and OG ($p < 0.05$; $\chi^2 = 31.689$). Attack/Counter-attack coefficient (A/CA) of OG (7.3) is higher than WC's (3.6). Types of victories determined in WC and OG are %63.7 ($f = 121$) and %73.8 (76) by point, 31.1% ($f = 59$) and 20.4% ($f = 80$) by technical superiority, 5.3% ($f = 10$) and 5.8% ($f = 6$) by fall, respectively. In the first and second period were determined mean technical points (TP_{mean}) 4.8 and 4.5 and mean technical points according to wrestling actions (WA_{mean}) 1.74 and 1.76 ($t = 0.488$, Cohen's $d = .031$) in WC and TP_{mean} 4.6 and 4.4 and WA_{mean} 1.66 and 1.69 ($t = 0.567$, Cohen's $d = .048$) in OG, respectively. Pull, action, and push combat frequencies are determined as 23 (2.8%), 654 (79.2%), and 149 (18%) in WC, and 10 (1.9%), 436 (84.8%), and 68 (13.2%) in OG, respectively. There is significant difference between bout combat type frequencies in WC and OG ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 17.732$).

Technical points scored according to matches and wrestling positions of the WC and the OG are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. There is no significant difference between the technical points scored in WC and OG ($p > 0.05$) with a small effect size ($\eta^2_p = .16$). In the two competitions, the most scored points are 2 technical points (72.5% in WC and 72.8% in OG). There is a significant difference between the points scored in standing and parterre position in both competitions ($p < 0.05$) with a large effect size (WC Cohen's $d = .633$ and OG Cohen's $d = .545$). S/P coefficient of OG (2.9) is higher than WC's (1.73). Technical points scored according to bout time are presented in Table 3. There is significant difference between mean technical points according to time in WC ($F_{time} = 13.137$; $\eta^2_p = .06$ medium) and OG ($F_{time} = 4.875$; $\eta^2_p = .04$ small).

Table 1. Technical points scored of WC and OG and comparisons.

Technical Point	WC			OG			F / η^2_p
	TP	%	TP/bt	TP	%	TP/m	
1	328	18.6	1.7	182	22.7	1.8	7.054 / .16
2	1276	72.5	6.7	584	72.8	5.7	
4	152	8.6	0.8	36	4.5	0.3	
5	5	0.3	0.03	0	0		
Total	1761	100	9.2	802	100	7.8	

TP: Total point, TP/bt: Mean total point per bout, WC: World Championship, OG: Olympic Games.

Table 2. Technical points scored according to wrestling position and comparisons.

Wrestling Position	WC				OG			
	TP / f	Mean	SD	t / d	f	Mean	SD	t / d
Standing	1115 / 656	1.66	0.8	7.389*	691/422	1.62	0.6	5.742*
Parterre	644 / 325	1.98	0.2	.633	240/124	1.94	0.3	.545
Total	1759 / 981	1.75	0.6		931/566	1.68	0.5	
S/P Coefficient	1.73				2.9			

*: There are statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$). S/P Coefficient: Standing-Parterre

Table 3. Frequencies of actions gained points and mean technical points scored according

Time (min)	WC				OG				F _{timecompet}
	f	M	SD	Pairwise	f	M	SD	Pairwise	
1	128	2.1	0.8		44	1.9	0.6		
2	182	1.8	0.6		78	1.7	0.7		
3	212	1.5	0.6	1-2,3,5,6*	116	1.5	0.5	1-3*	
4	145	1.9	0.5	2-3*	65	1.7	0.6	3-5*	
5	185	1.8	0.6		86	1.8	0.5		
6	151	1.7	0.7		93	1.6	0.6		
F_{time} / η_p^2	13.137 / .06				4.875 / .04				0.516

f: frequencies of actions gained points, M: mean technical points, SD: standard deviations, WC:

Frequencies and distribution of wrestling techniques are presented in Table 4. Wrestling techniques are divided into three groups. These are 1) Standing position: Take Down, Push to out, Leg Attack, Throws, Heel Tackle, and Miscellaneous, 2) Gut Wrench, Bring to danger position, Leg Lace, Crotch Lift, and 3) Other: Passive, Caution, and Challenge. Most wrestling techniques are performed standing (WC 58.8% and OG 68.2%). Leg Attack is the most used technique in the standing position (WC 17.9% and OG 21.8%). Gut Wrench is the most used technique in the parterre position (WC 8.7% and OG 7%).

Means of technical points according to weight categories and actions are presented in Table 5. The highest TPmean is 65 kg in WC and 74 kg in OG. There are the highest WAmean points in 74 kg, 86 kg, and 97 kg in WC (1.77) and 74 kg in OG (1.72).

Table 4. Frequency and distribution of technical movements.

Wrestling Techniques	WC			OG		
	f	%	f/match	f	%	f/match
Standing	592	58.8	3.11	382	68.2	3.70
Take Down	164	16.3	0.86	90	16.1	0.87
Push to out	152	15.1	0.80	110	19.6	1.06
Leg Attack	180	17.9	0.95	122	21.8	1.18
Throws	30	3	0.16	11	2	0.11
Heel Tackle	55	5.5	0.29	32	5.7	0.31
Miscellaneous	11	1.1	0.06	17	3	0.16
Parterre	241	24	1.27	85	15.2	0.82
Gut Wrench	88	8.7	0.45	39	7	0.37
Bring to a dangerous	85	8.5	0.46	28	5	0.27
Leg Lace	54	5.4	0.28	9	1.6	0.09
Crotch Lift	14	1.4	0.07	9	1.6	0.09
Other	173	17.2	9.1	93	16.6	0.90
Passive	125	12.4	0.66	63	11.3	0.61
Caution	23	2.3	0.12	17	3	0.17
Challenge	25	2.5	0.13	13	2.3	0.13
TOTAL	1006	100	5.29	560	100	5.43

Table 5. Mean of technical points/match according to weight categories and actions.

Weight Categories (kg)	WC			OG		
	TP _{mean}	WA _{mean}	SD	TP _{mean}	WA _{mean}	SD
57	9.8	1.75	0.64	9.9	1.68	0.59
65	10.2	1.73	0.68	9.4	1.60	0.49
74	9.5	1.77	0.64	10.2	1.72	0.51
86	9.5	1.77	0.59	9	1.40	0.46
97	9	1.77	0.77	7.4	1.70	0.79
125	7.5	1.75	0.59	9.4	1.67	0.53
TOTAL	<i>9.3</i>	<i>1.75</i>	<i>0.65</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>1.68</i>	<i>0.56</i>

TP_{mean}: Mean technical points /match according to weight categories. WA_{mean}: Mean of technical points according to wrestling actions.

Discussion and Conclusion

The objective of this study was to compare notational technical–tactical parameters of freestyle wrestling matches at the XXXII Summer OG and the 2022 WC. We hypothesized that matches in the Olympic Games would be more dynamic and yield higher quantitative performance metrics compared to the World Championships.

Wrestling match characteristics (e.g. duration, scoring systems, and periodic rule changes) can significantly influence not only the physiological and physical preparation of athletes but also their technical and tactical development. While numerous studies have explored tactical elements in wrestling, a lack of consensus and a heavy reliance on theoretical frameworks highlight the need for empirical data to guide technical-tactical training practices. In this regard, our findings address this gap by offering data-driven insights.

The results of the present study revealed that techniques yielding two points were the most frequently scored actions in both competitions. Additionally, more technical points were scored in the standing position than in the parterre position. A significant difference with a large effect size was observed, with the highest number of points earned within the first minute of bouts. These findings align with previous studies, such as Dokmanac et al. (2012), which showed that senior freestyle wrestlers primarily scored through standing position techniques during the 2011 World Championships. Further, significant differences were observed between the OG and WC in terms of points earned over time. The most frequently used standing techniques were leg attacks, takedowns, and push-outs, while gut wrenches dominated in the parterre position. The highest mean technical points across weight classes were observed in the 65 kg and 74 kg categories, whereas the lowest were in the 125 kg and 97 kg categories. These results are in line with earlier findings by Tünnemann (1998, 2011, 2016), and López-González et al. (2012), which consistently highlighted the prevalence of leg attacks, takedowns, push-outs, gut wrenches, and leg laces in high-level competition. Latyshev et al. (2017) reported an average of 7.5, 6.0, and 6.2 points per match in the 2016 OG for lightweight, middleweight, and heavyweight categories, respectively. Tünnemann (2011) also found an average of 7 points per match in the 2007 WC and 2008 OG. In contrast, our study found higher scoring averages: 9.3 points per match at Tokyo OG and 9.0 points per

match at the Belgrade WC. Furthermore, the average scoring rate per minute was higher in our study (1.75 at the 2022 WC and 1.67 at the 2020 OG) compared to the 1.32 reported by Dokmanac et al. (2012) in the 2011 WC. These increases may be attributed to recent rule changes intended to promote more active wrestling, particularly those concerning passivity.

Our findings also confirm that standing position techniques are more frequently employed than parterre techniques in freestyle wrestling—consistent with prior research. Attack movements were more prevalent than counter-attacks in both tournaments. Additionally, both the Standing/Parterre (S/P) coefficient and the Attack/Counter-attack (A/C) coefficient were higher at the Olympic Games than at the World Championships. This may be due to the increased competitiveness and prestige of the Olympic Games, held every four years. Victory by points represented the most common win type, especially at the World Championships (73.8% at WC and 63.7% at OG). This is in agreement with Arabacı et al. (2018), who reported a 72.3% point victory rate at the 2016 Rio Olympics. Interestingly, our results showed no significant difference in average technical points (TP_{mean}) or technical points per action (WA_{mean}) between the first and second periods in either tournament, corroborating the findings of Arabacı et al. (2018) and Tünnemann (2016). However, TP_{mean} and WA_{mean} were slightly higher in the first period and in the WC than in the OG, suggesting that wrestlers may be more effective in the earlier phases of bouts before fatigue sets in.

We indicate some limitations that may have influenced our findings. Firstly, the number of matches and participating athletes differed between the two competitions. Secondly, not all athletes competed in both tournaments. Lastly, referee decisions and potential errors should also be accounted for in notational analyses, as they may affect scoring dynamics. Future research should expand notational video analysis to include women's, Greco-Roman, and youth wrestling competitions. Furthermore, investigations into biomechanical factors, body segment movements, reaction times, and movement speeds during technical actions could provide additional insights into performance optimization.

In conclusion, the most impactful techniques in elite freestyle wrestling, such as leg attacks, takedowns, and push-outs, are predominantly executed in the standing position and often yield two points. Many scoring opportunities arise in the first period, particularly in the first minute of the match. These findings emphasize the importance of maximizing attack efficiency early in the bout and maintaining high physical and physiological readiness throughout. Accordingly, comprehensive technical-tactical training and education, beginning in youth and continuing through to elite levels, should be strategically planned to enhance performance in competitive wrestling settings.

Kısaltmalar / Abbreviations

SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
n	Örneklem sayısı
p	Anlamlılık değeri
TP _{Mean}	Mean technical points /match according to weight categories
WA _{Mean}	Mean of technical points according to wrestling actions.

Beyanlar / Declarations

Etik Onay ve Katılım Onayı / Ethics approval and consent to participate

Bu çalışmanın hazırlanma ve yazım sürecinde "Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi" kapsamında bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş olup; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamış ve bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir. Makale ile ilgili doğabilecek her türlü ihlallerde sorumluluk yazara aittir.

During the preparation and writing of this study, the principles of scientific integrity, ethics, and citation, as stipulated in the "Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive," were fully observed; no falsification was made on the collected data, and this study has not been submitted to any other academic publication platform for evaluation. The author bears full responsibility for any potential violations regarding the article.

Veri Ve Materyal Erişilebilirliği / Availability of data and material

Bu çalışmanın bulgularını destekleyen veriler, makul talepler üzerine sorumlu yazardan temin edilebilir. Veri seti yalnızca akademik amaçlar için erişilebilir olacak ve verilerin herhangi bir kullanımı, orijinal çalışmayı referans gösterecek ve katılımcıların gizliliğini koruyacaktır.

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The dataset will be accessible only for academic purposes, and any use of the data will recognize the original study and maintain the confidentiality of the participants.

Çıkar Çatışması / Competing interests

Yazarlar, bu makalede sunulan çalışmayı etkileyebilecek herhangi bir çıkar çatışması veya kişisel ilişkiye sahip olmadıklarını beyan etmektedirler.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Yazar Katkıları / Authors' Contribution Statement

Araştırma tasarımı, istatistiksel analiz, makale hazırlığı ve veri toplama süreçlerine tüm yazarlar eşit düzeyde katkıda bulunmuştur.

All authors contributed equally to the research design, statistical analysis, article preparation, and data collection processes.

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